

Portraits croisés Hussein ben Ali et Abdelaziz ibn Saoud

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Curriculum Vitae

Hussein ben Ali

1853 à Istanbul - 1931 à Amman, enterré à Jérusalem (Haram Ash-Sharif)
Clan des Banu Hashim, Tribu des Banu Quraysh

Chérif et Emir de la Mecque (1908-1924)

Roi du Hedjaz (1916-1924)

4 épouses (4^e noce avec la fille d'un Grand vizir)

5 fils et 3 filles

Descendant d'une lignée prestigieuse de Hassanides (Alides) Ahl Al Bayt أهل البيت

1908 : Charge officielle de chérif de la Mecque par sultan Abdul Hamid

1915 : Projet de révolte contre Ottomans du CUP-ITC soutenu par Faysal

1916 : Révolte arabe anti-Ottomane (T.E. Lawrence) par Faysal le 3^e fils. Projet de panarabisme de Hussein.

1920 : Sentiment de trahison par les mandats français et anglais en Syrie, Palestine et Iraq.

1921 : Royaumes hachémites d'Iraq et Jordanie pour ses fils Faysal et Abdallah

1924 : Défaite politique et militaire. Abdication en faveur d'Ali le fils aîné

1925 : Fin du royaume du Hedjaz et du Chérifat. Exil à Chypre puis Amman.

Abdelaziz ibn Saoud

1876 à Riyad -1953 à Ta'if
Clan des Banu Hanifa , Tribu des Banu Bakr

Roi du Nedj (1902-1932)

Roi du Hedjaz (1926-1932)

Roi d'Arabie (1932-1953)

32 épouses

53 fils et 36 filles

Dynastie bédouine et guerrière alliée à la confrérie guerrière wahhabite des Ikhwans

1891 : Défaite face au Al-Rashidi et exil au Koweit

1901 : Premier raids repoussés par Rashidi aidés par les Ottomans et les Al-Thani du Qatar

1902 : reconquête de Riyad

1905-1906 : retrait Ottoman et défaite des Al-Rashidi

1915-1922 : Offensive finale contre les Al- Rashidi (W. H. Shakespear). Finalisation conquête du Najd.

1924-1925 : Garanties aux Anglais sur le Golfe. Offensive contre le Royaume du Hedjaz.

1927 : traité et reconnaissance internationale du royaume du Nedj et du Hedjaz

1929 : Bataille de Sabilla, Ibn Saoud détruit la confrérie militaire des Ikhwans

1938 : Découverte de pétrole

1945 : Alliance stratégique avec USA (rencontre avec Roosevelt sur le USS Quincy)

Dynastie Al-Ashim الهاشميون

Chérifs et émirs de La Mecque (10è s.-1924)

Royaume du Hedjaz (1916-1925)

Royaume de Syrie (1918-1920)

Roi d'Irak (1921-1958)

Roi de Jordanie (1921-

Dynastie Al-Saoud - آل سعود

- Emirat de Diriyah (1744-1818)
- Emirat du Nejd (1828-1891)
- Emirat de Riyadh (1902-1913)
- Emirate du Nejd et Hasa (1913-1921)
- Sultanat du Nejd (1921-1926)
- Royaume du Hedjaz et Nejd (1926-1932)
- Royaume d'Arabie Saoudite (1932-)
- Capitale : Riyad

Dynastie Al-Rashid - آل رشيد

Emirat de Jebel Shammar
De 1836 à 1921
Capitale : Haïl

Descriptions par Thomas E. Lawrence

Portrait moral de Hussein dans "Seven pilars of Wisdom" (Lawrence était plus proche du fils Faysal que du père)

- "Hussein was honourable, shrewd, obstinate and deeply pious." Chapitre 5
- "Hussein trusted so much in God that he let his military sense lie fallow and thought Hejaz able to fight it out with Turkey on a fair field." Chapitre 5
- "Yet the school of Turkish politics was so ignoble that not even the best could graduate from it unaffected. Hussein when young had been honest, outspoken . . . and he learned not merely to suppress his speech, but to use speech to conceal his honest purpose. The art, over-indulged, became a vice from which he could not free himself. In old age ambiguity covered his every communication." Chapitre 14
- "Hussein was obstinate and crafty, and it might take weeks to force him out of his obstacles to an apology." Chapitre 106
- "King Hussein behaved (...) with endless circumlocution, showing no understanding of the grave effect of his incursion into Northern Army affairs. To clear his mind we sent him plain statements, which drew abusive but involved returns. (...) I had undesirable passages mutilated by rearranging their figures into nonsense (...), before handing them in code to Feisal. (...) Finally, there came a long message, the first half a lame apology and withdrawal of the mischievous proclamation, the second half a repetition of the offence in a new form. I suppressed the tail, and took the head marked 'Very urgent' to Feisal's (...) He was astonished, and gazed wonderingly at me, for the meek words were unlike his father's querulous obstinacy." Chapitre 106

Mentions de Abdulaziz Ibn Saud : seulement 4 passages dans "Seven pilars of Wisdom par TE Lawrence

- "Beyond lay various tribes owing obedience to Nuri Shaalan, the great Emir of the Ruwalla, who, after the Sherif and ibn Saud and ibn Rashid, was the fourth figure among the precarious princes of the desert." Chapitre 30
- "They began to tell me long stories of Captain Shakespear, who had been received by ibn Saud in Riyadh as a personal friend, and had crossed Arabia from the Persian Gulf to Egypt; and been at last killed in battle by the Shammar in a set-back which the champions of Nejd had suffered during one of their periodic wars." Chapitre 45

Descriptions par Timothy J. Paris

“Few rulers, East or West, presented a more **difficult personality**. **Uncompromising, truculent, immune to reason**, at times apparently **irrational**, King Husain posed a challenge to even the most imperturbable British Agents. And it was not just the British who had become exasperated with the King: by 1919 he had alienated many of his own subjects in the Hijaz, who had grown weary of his **autocratic and arbitrary rule**. Had the effect of Husain’s authority been limited to the Hijaz, few problems might have been posed by his continued rule. But the King controlled the holy places and administered the hajj, and this meant that his authority potentially affected millions throughout Islam. Most agreed that **Husain’s administration of the pilgrimage was execrable**. Not only did he increase the scope and amount of pilgrimage fees and costs, he **failed to share fairly the money** thus generated with the tribes. As a consequence, **he lost tribal support**, and by 1923 could no longer ensure the safety of the hajj. »

BRITAIN, THE HASHEMITES AND ARAB RULE, 1920-1925, par Timothy J. Paris - Page 345

“By 1924, Ibn Saud had so **conditioned British official opinion in his favour** that he hardly needed to conquer the Hijaz. Husain did it for him. Thus, by the time the Kuwait Conference failed in the spring of 1924, blame was laid at the feet of Husain, even though it was obvious that Ibn Saud had caused the Conference to break up. Ibn Saud was **clearly more powerful than Husain**, and had been since 1919. »

Ib. - Page 348

Descriptions par correspondance du Foreign Office

Refus d'Hussein de cautionner l'attribution des mandats à la suite de la conférence de San Remo de mai 1920

who appears from our latest reports to be in a more than usually unamiable frame of mind. Feisal also will be told that if, with his father's and brother's consent, he becomes a candidate for Mesopotamia and is accepted by the Council of that country

In short, I say that it should be clearly understood that I never rose for the sake of wealth, property or sovereignty, or for my sons to be kings, but in the interest of the Arabs and Arab independence. I do not mind if you have Ibn Saud, Idrisi or any capable person to take over the work from me. But it is most essential that His Majesty's Government should carry out the agreements, because they are not only in the interest of the Arabs and the Moslems generally, but of the British themselves.

I have been told by His Majesty's Government that

King Hussein's statements, April 1921

Descriptions par correspondance du Foreign Office

It is characteristic of King Hussein that he is offering the High Commissioner for Palestine a treaty "on reasonable terms." King Hussein is always reasonable; it is only the world he lives in which is unreasonable. But it is difficult to see what sort of

even though we may have doubts as to the good faith of His Hashimite Majesty and his intention to abide by anything he may sign. The unregulated situation is dangerous, in that it gives the King greater scope for mad outbursts of hostility and obstruction.

The "Kible" has published subjects from treating him as they treat pilgrims.

It would be interesting to see the Hedjaz budget at the present time. Unfortunately there is no budget except, probably in a very vague form, in the head of King Hussein. The King is raising large sums in Transjordan by means of drafts.

all consignments of goods they receive. The King's visit to Amman has increased his megalomania. He is said to have ordered rolling-stock for the Hedjaz Railway, and at the same time he is buying two steamers to carry pilgrims.

Consul Bullard to M. MacDonald, February 1924

Descriptions par correspondance du Foreign Office

“Mr. Churchill is of the opinion that King Hussein’s recent conduct has been of a character which would make his abdication an event to be desired in British interests and hopes by a prompt acquiescence in the situation he may be led to take the steps indicated.”

Bullard to Fuad al-Khatib, March
1924

Hedjaz army has almost disappeared. Commander-in-chief says that Mecca will fall in two or three days. King declares intention to die there. Not a man in the capital is prepared to fight, and tribes are indifferent.

I fear abdication, flight or death of ruler is first step towards peace.

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Consul Bullard to M. MacDonald, September 1924

allowed to defend Hedjaz against Ibn Saud. I think your request will only make me more respected by my own people, since you treat me like this, although I was friendly with yours. Death would be better than life; so far as British are concerned it would be better for me to die.—(Signed) KING HUSSEIN, dated

King Hussein to Secretary of Foreign Affairs, May 1925

Descriptions par correspondance du Foreign Office

4. Public security is perfect, not only in Mecca, but everywhere else within the territory held by Ibn Saud. This has been established by punishing the least disorder with the most ruthless severity.

the essence of these long talks can be summed up in a few words: Ibn Saud would be glad of help (probably financial) from His Majesty's Government, and in return he would forget his hatred and distrust of Feisal and Abdullah; and in order to enhance his value in the eyes of His Majesty's Government, he perhaps tends to exaggerate the importance of the advances made by the Italian and possibly the French authorities.

Consul Bullard to Austen Chamberlain, May 1925

(Telegraphic.)
PLEASE inform Ibn Saud that the King has received his telegram of 27th December and thanks him for the sentiments of friendship therein expressed. His Majesty is glad to learn that war is ended, and gratified that his representative was enabled to contribute to prevention of bloodshed.

Austen Chamberlain to acting agent M. Jordan, January¹² 1926

Conclusion

- **Des personnalités très différentes**
- **Abdelaziz ibn Saoud**
 - *Un chef de guerre, exilé et dépossédé alors qu'il était enfant*
 - *Une alliance historique (1744) avec une confrérie guerrière investie d'une mission religieuse: Les Wahhabites (puritains de l'Islam) d'obédience Hanbalite, « réformée Ibn Taymiyya »*
 - *Une approche méthodique de reconquête : d'abord les Al-Rashid, puis les Al-Ashim*
 - *Une gestion intelligente et cynique de ses alliances (Koweït, Ottomans, Anglais, Ikhwans, Américains)*
 - *Une liberté d'action et de moyens qui n'est pas (trop) dépendante des subsides étrangers*
 - *Une machine de guerre bien rodée*
 - *Des actions progressives et séquencées, calculées et préparées, pragmatisme dans les négociations*
 - *Une ambition limitée à la péninsule arabique sans irrédentisme trop menaçant vers le nord, le Golfe persique et l'océan indien*
- **Hussein ben Ali**
 - *Un héritier d'une famille prestigieuse et notable dans l'Empire ottoman*
 - *Une rébellion d'opportunité portée par son fils Faysal*
 - *Une ambition panarabe et d'union personnelle des nations arabes sans compromis, inquiétante et déstabilisante pour les nations mandataires*
 - *Califat Hachémite mort-né*
 - *Des revendications territoriales inopportunes*
 - *Palestine et Déclaration Balfour sur le foyer juif*
 - *Accords Sykes-Picot transformés à la conférence de San Remo en Mandat français de Syrie-Liban et Mandat anglais d'Iraq*
 - *Des déclarations programmatiques ambitieuses et inquiétantes , caractère instable, revendicatif, mégalomane et intransigeant*

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